

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE SURFACTANTS SYNTHESIZED FROM THE REACTION OF LAURIC ACID WITH POLYETHYLENEPOLYAMINE.

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Abstract: In this work, mono and Gemini type substances were obtained from the reaction of lauric acid with polyethylene polyamine in two different proportions and their comparative analysis was carried out. The structure of the obtained final products was confirmed by IR spectroscopy. A number of important physical parameters were calculated by measuring the surface activity and electrical conductivity of the compounds. Finally, the petrocollecting and petrodispersing abilities of surfactants in water basins with different salinity were checked.

Key words: surfactant, lauric acid, polyetylenepolyamine, petrocollecting, petrodispersing

Introduction: Considering the crucial role of water in supporting life on Earth, the increasing contamination of this vital resource has become a significant crisis, prompting collaboration among various individuals, including scientists, environmentalists, engineers, and ordinary citizens. The degradation of water quality is primarily attributed to human activities, with a notable and hazardous form of organic pollution being oil leakage, often detected during incidents like groundings, platform accidents, and supertanker mishaps [1]. To address oil spills and slicks, it is crucial to leverage evolving technologies, including physical, chemical, thermal, or in-situ burning, as well as bioremediation [2]. Rapid and efficient treatment of oil spills is imperative, and chemical treatment has emerged as a widely adopted approach, utilizing compounds such as demulsifiers, herders, dispersants, sorbents, solidifiers, and elasticity agents [3-4]. This research specifically focuses on chemical treatment using surfactants synthesized from the reaction of fatty acids with polyamines.

Materials and methods: The reaction mechanisms are shown below:

Figure 1. Reaction mechanism of the surfactants a) mono-Salt 1; b) Gemini-Salt 2
 The surface tensions of the synthesized salts in water with different concentrations at the air-water interface were measured with a Tensiometer. Isotherms of surface tension dependence on solids were constructed and are listed in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Surface tension of the synthesized salts

According to the graph, the KMQ point was determined for both compounds and the surface activity parameters were determined. The Gemini-type compound has a surface tension reduction of 26.73 mN/m at the air-water interface at concentrations of $1.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol/L and higher. In addition, the surface pressure of the substance with dimer structure is greater than that of mono structure. It can be concluded that, Gemini surfactants shows better surface activity properties than its monomer. It also proves that this product will contain better properties in the removal of oil spills in which surface activity plays a huge role on it.

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